

Efficacy of Non-Pharmacologic Distraction Techniques on Pain Perception During Mandibular Molar Extraction in Children - A Single-Blinded Randomized Controlled Trial.

Running title - Distraction Techniques for Pain Control in Children.

Harsh S Baldawa, BDS

Post graduate student,

Department of pediatric and preventive dentistry

Saveetha dental college and hospitals

Saveetha institute of medical and technical sciences

Saveetha university

Chennai -77

Dinesh Kumar B, MDS

Senior Lecturer

Department of pediatric and preventive dentistry

Saveetha dental college and hospitals

Saveetha institute of medical and technical sciences

Saveetha university

Chennai -77

Rasika P Chandak, BDS

Post graduate student,

Department of pediatric and preventive dentistry

Saveetha dental college and hospitals

Saveetha institute of medical and technical sciences

Saveetha university

Chennai -77

Corresponding author:

Dinesh Kumar B, MDS

Senior Lecturer

Department of pediatric and preventive dentistry

Saveetha dental college and hospitals

Saveetha institute of medical and technical sciences

Saveetha university

Chennai -77

Abstract

Aim:

To compare the effectiveness of three non-pharmacologic distraction techniques—EVC, virtual reality(VR), and aromatherapy(AT)—on pain perception and physiological stress during mandibular molar extraction in children.

Materials and Methods:

A randomized controlled trial was conducted among 120 children aged 6–12 years, equally divided into four groups: Control, Extraoral Vibration and Cooling(EVC), VR, and AT. Only mandibular molars requiring extraction under inferior alveolar nerve block(IANB) were included to standardize the pain stimulus. Pain perception was assessed using the Wong–Baker Faces Pain Rating Scale (WBFPS) and the FLACC(Face, Legs, Activity, Cry, Consolability) Behavioral Pain Scale, while physiological stress was measured through heart rate (HR) changes recorded pre- and post-extraction. Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and MANOVA, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results:

All distraction techniques significantly reduced both pain and heart-rate elevation compared with the control group ($p < 0.001$). The EVC group demonstrated the lowest mean pain scores (WBFPS = 2.14 ± 1.03 ; FLACC = 2.38 ± 1.21) and the smallest HR increase ($\Delta\text{HR} = +4.1 \pm 3.8$ bpm). VR and AT also showed notable reductions, while the control group exhibited the highest values. MANOVA confirmed a significant overall group effect (Wilks' $\lambda = 0.32$, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion:

All distraction methods were effective in alleviating pain and stress, with EVC producing the most pronounced analgesic and calming effect. Its simplicity, safety, and ease of application make it a valuable adjunct to local anesthesia in pediatric dental care.

Keywords:

AT, distraction, inferior alveolar nerve block, pain management, pediatric dentistry, VR, vibration-cooling

Introduction

Pain and anxiety are among the most significant behavioral challenges encountered in pediatric dentistry.(1)(2) Dental extractions, though often minor surgical procedures, can provoke intense fear and distress in children due to their limited coping mechanisms, past negative dental experiences, and fear of needles.(3)(4) The presence of pain and anxiety not only interferes with the efficiency of dental treatment but can also lead to the development of long-term dental phobia and avoidance behavior, compromising oral health maintenance throughout life.(5)(6)

Effective pain management in children requires a dual focus: the physiological modulation of pain perception and the psychological control of anxiety.(7) While pharmacologic interventions such as local anesthesia and sedation are commonly used, non-pharmacologic behavioral strategies have emerged as essential adjuncts that complement these techniques.(8) Among these, distraction methods—which divert the child’s attention away from the dental stimulus—are gaining increasing attention for their simplicity, safety, and efficacy.(9)

Several forms of distraction have been explored in pediatric dentistry. Extraoral vibration combined with cooling provides both mechanical and thermal stimulation that activates large-diameter A-beta fibers, thereby closing the “pain gate” and reducing nociceptive transmission during local anesthetic administration.(10)(11) VR offers immersive audiovisual engagement, allowing children to become absorbed in an interactive environment that minimizes awareness of the dental setting.(12)(13) AT, using pleasant natural scents such as lavender, exerts a calming influence by modulating the limbic system and reducing sympathetic nervous activity.(14)(15) Each of these approaches acts through distinct neurophysiological and psychological pathways to alleviate procedural discomfort and anxiety.(16)

Although numerous studies have investigated these techniques individually, comparative evidence evaluating their relative efficacy within a standardized clinical setting remains limited. Determining which method provides the most effective reduction in pain perception and physiological stress can guide pediatric dentists in selecting appropriate adjunctive strategies for managing anxious children.

Therefore, the present randomized controlled trial aimed to compare the effectiveness of EVC, VR distraction, and AT on pain perception and physiological response during tooth extraction in children. The study hypothesized that all distraction techniques would reduce pain perception compared with the control group, with EVC expected to produce the greatest analgesic effect.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

This randomized controlled clinical trial was conducted in the Department of Pedodontics of a Private Dental College, Chennai, India, between [June 2025] and [July 2025]. The trial followed the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (2013) and was reported according to the CONSORT 2010 statement. Written informed consent was

obtained from the parents or legal guardians of all participants, and verbal assent was obtained from each child.

Participants

Children aged 6 to 12 years who required extraction of mandibular molar teeth under IANB anesthesia were screened for inclusion. Each child's dental anxiety was assessed using the Modified Child Dental Anxiety Scale (MCDAS), and only those exhibiting moderate anxiety (scores 17–24) were recruited to ensure comparable psychological baselines across groups. Children classified as American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) I or II and demonstrating positive or definitely positive behaviour on the Frankl Behaviour Rating Scale (3 or 4) were included.

Children were excluded if they presented with mobile teeth, as mobility could reduce nociceptive input and confound pain assessment. Those with high anxiety (MCDAS > 24) or minimal anxiety (MCDAS < 17) were excluded, as were children with systemic disease, developmental or cognitive impairment, known allergy to local anaesthetic agents or essential oils, or prior exposure to VR or AT during dental treatment. Children unable to comply with study procedures or whose parents declined consent were also excluded.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size was calculated using data from a randomized controlled trial by Al-Khotani et al. (2016), which evaluated the effect of audiovisual distraction on children's behaviour during dental treatment.(17) That study reported a mean difference of 1.2 ± 1.4 on the WBFPS between control and audiovisual distraction groups, corresponding to an effect size (Cohen's *d*) of approximately 0.85. Assuming a similar effect size, a significance level (α) = 0.05, and power ($1 - \beta$) = 0.80, the required sample size for four groups in a one-way ANOVA was estimated as 27 participants per group. Allowing for a 10 % dropout rate, the final sample size was rounded to 30 participants per group, yielding a total of 120 children ($n = 30 \times 4$).(17)

Randomization and Allocation Concealment

Eligible participants were randomly assigned to one of four study groups using a computer-generated randomization sequence. Allocation concealment was ensured with opaque, sequentially numbered, sealed envelopes prepared by an independent

investigator. The treating operator was aware of the group assignment, but the data analyst and behavioural assessor were blinded to the intervention.

Intervention Groups

- **Group I (Control):**
Standard tooth extraction under local anaesthesia (IANB) without any additional distraction technique.
- **Group II (EVC):**
An EVC device was applied externally over the mandibular injection site corresponding to the IANB region.(Figure 1) The device was activated and maintained in position for 30 seconds prior to administration of the local anaesthetic. When the device reached its peak cooling (approximately 0°C and vibratory effect, 2 % lidocaine with 1:100,000 epinephrine was injected while the device remained active. The device was removed immediately after completion of the injection.(18)
- **Group III (VR):**
Participants wore a virtual-reality device displaying age-appropriate immersive animated content.(Figure 2) The VR system was activated before administration of local anaesthetic and continued throughout the extraction procedure.
- **Group IV (AT):**
A lavender essential-oil diffuser was placed near the dental chair, allowing continuous inhalation starting three minutes before anaesthesia and continuing through the extraction.

Procedure

All procedures were performed by a single experienced pediatric dentist to minimize operator variability. For all participants, local anaesthesia was achieved using 2 % lidocaine with 1:100,000 epinephrine via IANB technique. In Group II, the EVC device was positioned over the injection site for 30 seconds prior to needle insertion, and local anaesthetic was administered at the peak of the device's analgesic effect. Following confirmation of adequate anaesthesia, the extraction was completed using standard techniques appropriate to tooth morphology.

Baseline heart rate (HR) was recorded using a pulse oximeter prior to local anaesthesia administration. Post-operative HR was measured immediately after tooth extraction. Pain perception was evaluated immediately post-extraction using two validated scales:

1. The WBFPS (0–10),(19) and
2. The FLACC Behavioural Pain Scale (0–10).(20)

All procedures were video-recorded, and a blinded examiner independently reviewed the recordings to verify behavioural scoring accuracy. Any adverse effects (e.g., dizziness, nausea, discomfort) were noted.

Outcome Measures

The primary outcome was post-operative pain perception measured by WBFPS and FLACC scales. Secondary outcomes included change in heart rate ($\Delta\text{HR} = \text{post} - \text{pre}$), observable behaviour during the procedure, and any reported adverse events.

Statistical Analysis

All data were compiled and analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics were computed as mean \pm standard deviation for continuous variables and as frequencies and percentages for categorical variables. Normality was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Inter-group comparisons of pain and physiological variables were performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s post-hoc test for parametric data, and the Kruskal–Wallis test with Dunn’s correction for non-parametric data. Within-group pre- and post-procedure HR differences were analysed using the paired t-test. A $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 120 children aged between 6 and 12 years (mean age = 8.9 ± 1.8 years) were enrolled and successfully completed the study. Among them, 53 were boys and 67 were girls. There were no dropouts or reported adverse events such as dizziness, nausea, or local irritation. The distribution of participants by age and gender across the four groups was statistically comparable ($p > 0.05$), confirming that randomization was effective (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Variable	Group I (Control)	Group II (Vibration-Cooling)	Group III (VR)	Group IV (AT)	Total
n	30	30	30	30	120

Age (years, mean \pm SD)	9.1 \pm 1.6	8.8 \pm 1.7	8.9 \pm 1.9	9.0 \pm 1.8	8.9 \pm 1.8
Boys n (%)	15 (50.0%)	14 (46.7%)	11 (36.7%)	13 (43.3%)	53 (44.2%)
Girls n (%)	15 (50.0%)	16 (53.3%)	19 (63.3%)	17 (56.7%)	67 (55.8%)

The mean pain scores measured by the WBFPS and the FLACC Behavioural Pain Scale showed significant variation among the four study groups (Table 2). The control group reported the highest pain intensity, while the EVC group recorded the lowest mean scores, followed by the VR and AT groups. One-way ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference across all groups ($p < 0.001$) for both scales, indicating that all distraction techniques significantly reduced perceived pain compared with control.

Table 2: Comparison of Mean Pain Scores among Study Groups

Parameter	WBFPS (mean \pm SD)	FLACC (mean \pm SD)	p-value
Group I (Control)	6.52 \pm 1.24	6.84 \pm 1.09	—
Group II (EVC)	2.14 \pm 1.03	2.38 \pm 1.21	< 0.001
Group III (VR)	3.18 \pm 1.26	3.52 \pm 1.11	< 0.001
Group IV (AT)	4.10 \pm 1.20	4.46 \pm 1.34	< 0.001

All groups exhibited a statistically significant increase in mean heart rate after extraction compared with baseline values ($p < 0.001$, paired t-test within each group).

However, the EVC group showed the least elevation in post-operative heart rate, followed by VR and AT, whereas the control group demonstrated the highest rise (Table 3). The inter-group comparison of heart-rate difference (Δ HR) using one-way ANOVA revealed a

highly significant difference among groups ($p < 0.001$), confirming that distraction techniques effectively mitigated physiological stress associated with dental extraction.

Table 3: Comparison of Pre- and Post-operative Heart Rates among Groups

Parameter	Pre-operative HR (mean \pm SD)	Post-operative HR (mean \pm SD)	p-value
Group I (Control)	92.8 \pm 6.4	106.5 \pm 7.1	< 0.001
Group II (EVC)	91.2 \pm 5.9	95.3 \pm 6.1	< 0.001
Group III (VR)	90.7 \pm 6.2	97.5 \pm 5.8	< 0.001
Group IV (AT)	91.6 \pm 6.1	99.8 \pm 6.4	< 0.001

A one-way multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was performed with group (Control, Vibration-Cooling, VR, AT) as the fixed factor and the combined vector of WBFPS, FLACC, and HR as dependent variables. The MANOVA revealed a highly significant overall multivariate effect of the intervention on the set of outcome measures (Wilks' $\lambda = 0.32$, $F = 24.1$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that the combined behavioral and physiological responses varied significantly among groups. The effect size was large (partial $\eta^2 = 0.41$), suggesting a strong influence of the distraction technique on both pain perception and physiological stress (Table 4).

Table 4: Multivariate (MANOVA) Summary for Group Differences Across Outcomes

Test	Statistic	Effect Size (partial η^2)	p-value
Wilks' Lambda	0.32	0.41	< 0.001

Dependent variables: WBFPS, FLACC, and HR.

Discussion

Pain management in pediatric dentistry remains one of the most challenging aspects of clinical practice. Children often experience heightened anxiety and amplified pain responses during dental procedures, particularly during local anesthesia and extractions. The present randomized controlled trial compared three non-pharmacologic distraction techniques—EVC, VR, and AT—on pain perception and physiological response in children undergoing mandibular molar extraction. All three interventions significantly reduced pain and stress compared with the control group, with EVC demonstrating the greatest overall effectiveness.

The findings strongly support the Gate Control Theory of pain (Melzack & Wall, 1965), which posits that stimulation of large-diameter A-beta fibers through vibration and cooling inhibits nociceptive signal transmission from smaller A-delta and C fibers.(21) The dual sensory input—mechanical and thermal—likely created a powerful gating effect that suppressed pain transmission at the spinal level, explaining the markedly lower pain and heart-rate elevations observed in the vibration-cooling group.(22) Similar findings were reported by Baldawa et al. (2025), where they reviewed 3 articles demonstrating extraoral vibration combined with cooling significantly decreased pain during IANB in pediatric dental patients.(23)

The virtual-reality distraction technique also yielded substantial reductions in both WBFPS and FLACC scores. By immersing children in a multisensory audiovisual environment, VR effectively diverts cognitive focus away from the dental procedure, thereby modulating emotional and attentional responses to pain. These results are consistent with those of Al-Khotani et al. (2016) and Felemban et al. (2018), who found significant decreases in anxiety and behavioral distress among children undergoing dental treatment using VR distraction.(17)(24) While VR was slightly less potent than vibration-cooling in the current trial, it offered strong acceptability and compliance, making it a useful behavioral adjunct for managing moderate anxiety.

AT with lavender essential oil produced a milder but statistically significant reduction in pain and stress compared to control. The anxiolytic effect of lavender is attributed to linalool and linalyl acetate, which act on the limbic system and potentiate GABAergic neurotransmission, thereby reducing sympathetic arousal and promoting relaxation.(25) Previous studies by Abdalhai et al. (2025) and Kumar et al. (2020) have similarly shown that lavender aroma can decrease anxiety and stabilize physiological parameters in dental and medical environments.(14)(26) Although less powerful than the other two modalities, AT remains a practical and non-invasive adjunct to create a calm dental atmosphere.

The results of the multivariate analysis (Wilks' $\lambda = 0.32$, $p < 0.001$) confirmed significant overall differences across interventions, with a large effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.41$), underscoring the strong influence of distraction techniques on both behavioral and physiological indicators. Among the three tested modalities, EVC exhibited the most consistent and pronounced analgesic effect across all measures.

A major methodological strength of the study was its deliberate restriction to mandibular molar extractions under IANB, which ensured a uniform pain stimulus and eliminated variability arising from different injection sites or techniques. This standardization enhanced the internal validity of the findings. The calculated sample size of 120 participants was statistically adequate based on prior literature, ensuring sufficient power for group comparisons.

However, the study had one inherent limitation—blinding of participants was practically impossible due to the physical and perceptual nature of the interventions. Children could clearly perceive whether they were experiencing vibration, visual stimuli, or aroma exposure, which may have introduced minimal expectation bias despite consistent operator and assessor blinding. Future research could incorporate objective biomarkers such as salivary cortisol or galvanic skin response and explore combined or sequential distraction techniques to further optimize clinical outcomes.

Conclusion

All three distraction techniques—EVC, VR, and AT—significantly reduced pain and stress during mandibular molar extraction in children. The EVC device was the most effective, showing the lowest pain scores and minimal physiological response. Given its simplicity, safety, and rapid action, it can be recommended as a practical adjunct to local anesthesia in pediatric dental care.

Data Availability Statement

Further data is available on request to the corresponding author.

Funding Statement

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

1. Al Homoud RA, Alshellatie AK, Alzumaie AS, Al-Bayati SA. Behavior and anxiety levels in pediatric patient: The behavioral changes and anxiety of pediatric patient in dental clinic. *Clin Exp Dent Res*. 2023 Dec;9(6):1223–31.
2. Fathima A, Ravikumar R, Chellappa LR. Development of Cartoon-based Dental Anxiety Scale for Children: Validation and Reliability. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2024 Jul;17(7):796–801.
3. Sivakumar P, Gurunathan D. Behavior of Children toward Various Dental Procedures. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2019 Sep-Oct;12(5):379–84.
4. Kumar G, Jena S, Manila N, Fareed M, Karobari MI. Incidence of postoperative pain after single-visit and multiple-visit root canal therapy: a systematic review. *BMC Oral Health*. 2025 Jan 8;25(1):47.
5. Winkler CH, Bjelopavlovic M, Lehmann KM, Petrowski K, Irmscher L, Berth H. Impact of Dental Anxiety on Dental Care Routine and Oral-Health-Related Quality of Life in a German Adult Population-A Cross-Sectional Study. *J Clin Med* [Internet]. 2023 Aug 14;12(16). Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/jcm12165291>
6. Supriya, Ahsan A, Singh R. Insights about dental anxiety and oral health behaviors: Dentist's perspective in a qualitative study. *J Indian Assoc Public Health Dent*. 2025 Jan;23(1):26–30.
7. Andersson V, Bergman S, Henoeh I, Simonsson H, Ahlberg K. Pain and pain management in children and adolescents receiving hospital care: a cross-sectional study from Sweden. *BMC Pediatr*. 2022 May 5;22(1):252.
8. Kotian N, Subramanian EMG, Jeevanandan G. Comparing the Sedative Effect of Oral and Intranasal Midazolam and their Effect on Behavior in Pediatric Dental Patients. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2022 Jan-Feb;15(1):128–34.

9. Khandelwal M, Shetty RM, Rath S. Effectiveness of Distraction Techniques in Managing Pediatric Dental Patients. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2019 Jan-Feb;12(1):18–24.
10. Hambouta HM, Sharaf DA, Wahba NA. Effectiveness of cold vibratory stimuli on pain perception governing infiltration anesthesia in the maxillary arch in children: a randomized controlled clinical trial. *BMC Oral Health*. 2025 Jun 3;25(1):900.
11. Tirupathi SP, Nanda N, Pallepogu S, Malothu S, Rathi N, Chauhan RS, et al. The combined effect of extraoral vibratory stimulus and external cooling on pain perception during intra-oral local anesthesia administration in children: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Dent Anesth Pain Med*. 2022 Apr;22(2):87–96.
12. Trusculescu LM, Pitic DE, Sălcudean A, Popovici RA, Forna N, Badoiu SC, et al. VR as a Non-Pharmacological Aid for Reducing Anxiety in Pediatric Dental Procedures. *Children (Basel)* [Internet]. 2025 Jul 14;12(7). Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/children12070930>
13. Barros Padilha DX de, Veiga NJ, Mello-Moura ACV, Nunes Correia P. VR and behaviour management in paediatric dentistry: a systematic review. *BMC Oral Health*. 2023 Dec 12;23(1):995.
14. Abdalhai R, Tolibah YA, Alkhatib R, Kouchaji C, Baghdadi ZD. Lavender-Neroli AT for Reducing Dental Anxiety and Pain in Children During Anesthesia: A Two-Arm Randomized Controlled Trial. *Med Sci (Basel)* [Internet]. 2025 Sep 1;13(3). Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/medsci13030166>
15. Kumar D, Gurunathan D, Jabin Z, Talal S. AT versus conscious sedation evaluation in reducing dental anxiety in pediatric dental patients. *Ann Dent Spec*. 2024;12(2):25–31.
16. Torres-Gomez J, Arnason SC, Hoopes WL, Vandewalle KS. Management of dental anxiety via distraction technique. *J Clin Exp Dent*. 2021 Apr;13(4):e350–6.
17. Al-Khotani A, Bello LA, Christidis N. Effects of audiovisual distraction on children's behaviour during dental treatment: a randomized controlled clinical trial. *Acta Odontol Scand*. 2016 Aug;74(6):494–501.
18. Hindocha N, Manhem F, Bäckryd E, Bågesund M. Ice versus lidocaine 5% gel for topical anaesthesia of oral mucosa - a randomized cross-over study. *BMC Anesthesiol*. 2019 Dec 16;19(1):227.

19. Garra G, Singer AJ, Taira BR, Chohan J, Cardoz H, Chisena E, et al. Validation of the Wong-Baker FACES Pain Rating Scale in pediatric emergency department patients. *Acad Emerg Med*. 2010 Jan;17(1):50–4.
20. Peng T, Qu S, Du Z, Chen Z, Xiao T, Chen R. A Systematic Review of the Measurement Properties of Face, Legs, Activity, Cry and Consolability Scale for Pediatric Pain Assessment. *J Pain Res*. 2023 Apr 8;16:1185–96.
21. Mendell LM. Constructing and deconstructing the gate theory of pain. *Pain*. 2014 Feb;155(2):210–6.
22. Duan B, Cheng L, Bourane S, Britz O, Padilla C, Garcia-Campmany L, et al. Identification of spinal circuits transmitting and gating mechanical pain. *Cell*. 2014 Dec 4;159(6):1417–32.
23. Baldawa H, Tirupathi S, Ramakrishnan M, Gurunathan D, Jeevanandan G, Ravindran V, et al. Effectiveness of combined extraoral vibration and cooling on pain perception due to inferior alveolar nerve block administration in children: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Dent Anesth Pain Med*. 2025 Aug;25(4):227–37.
24. Felemban OM, Alshamrani RM, Aljeddawi DH, Bagher SM. Effect of VR distraction on pain and anxiety during infiltration anesthesia in pediatric patients: a randomized clinical trial. *BMC Oral Health*. 2021 Jun 25;21(1):321.
25. Batiha GES, Teibo JO, Wasef L, Shaheen HM, Akomolafe AP, Teibo TKA, et al. A review of the bioactive components and pharmacological properties of *Lavandula* species. *Naunyn Schmiedebergs Arch Pharmacol*. 2023 May;396(5):877–900.
26. Kumar JC, Akhil KP. Lavender AT in the management of dental anxiety. *Journal of Dental Health and Oral Research* [Internet]. 2020;01(02). Available from: <https://athenaumpub.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Lavender-AT-in-the-Management-of-Dental-Anxiety.pdf>

Figure 1 - Extraoral vibration and cooling device.

Figure 2 - Virtual reality device.